

THE ROLE OF STYLISTICS IN TRANSLATION ACTIVITIES

Muborakxon Tuychiyeva Bahodir qizi

(Student of SamSIFL)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10417839>

Annotation. This article is devoted to usage of stylistics in translation process. Modern translation activity is associated with original texts of different styles. It is not at all easy to convey the author's feelings, state, and experiences during translation. For this, it is not enough to have a large vocabulary, although this plays an important role. It is important to be able to recognize expression in the translated text. The translator sometimes deliberately resorts to the use of stylistic devices to give greater expressiveness and sensuality to the created text.

Key words: psychological translation, literary translation, historical translation, stylistic structure

Translating metaphors, metonymies, comparisons, allusions forces more than one translator to treat the work very thoughtfully. Note that the problem of translating expression confuses not only beginners, but also professional translators.

As we know, translation is a complex, multifaceted phenomenon, individual aspects of which can be the subject of study by different sciences. Translation reveals psychological, literary, ethnographic and other aspects of human activity, and also combines the history of translation activity in a particular country or countries. Thus, many linguists, depending on the subject of research, highlight the following aspects:

- psychological translation studies (psychology of translation),
- literary translation studies (theory of artistic or literary translation),
- ethnographic translation studies,
- historical translation studies" [1], etc.

Certain aspects of translation studies significantly complement each other, striving for a comprehensive description of translation activities.

But in order for the translator to decide which synonym he should use in this particular text, he needs to turn to the stylistic structure, to the stylistic features of the original of the entire work. Thus, the specialist has an excellent opportunity to select stylistic and rhetorical figures and tropes. It is stylistic consistency that will be the final criterion for the translator, which will help him in selecting the necessary vocabulary, grammatical forms and sentence structures.

Translation of stylistic devices that carry a figurative charge of a work often causes difficulties for translators due to the national characteristics of the stylistic systems of different languages. All linguists emphasize the need to preserve the image of the original in translation, rightly believing that, first of all, the translator should strive to reproduce the function of the technique, and not the technique itself [3].

When conveying stylistic figures of speech - comparisons, epithets, metaphors, proverbs, etc. - the translator needs to decide each time: it is advisable to preserve the underlying image or it should be replaced by another in translation. The reason for the replacement may be the peculiarities of Russian word usage, compatibility of words, etc.

The stylistic aspect of translation is necessary for the translator; without it, a beautiful translation could not and cannot be obtained. It is the stylistic aspect of the language that is

responsible not only for the translation from the original language into the target language, but also for the characteristics and skill of the translator. After all, the translation of the original depends on how the translator is able to convey the meaning of stylistic units. Expression during translation gives greater expressiveness to the source text. It is natural that for literary scholars, linguists, cultural experts and philosophers the main and most interesting problems are related to literary translation, the translation of literary speech. Means of expression include: metaphor, metonymy, comparison, allusions, quotes, catchphrases, proverbs and sayings. When translating, the most difficult thing for a translator to do is translate such stylistic figures of speech as metaphor, epithets, comparisons, proverbs, etc. Of course, a translator can translate without paying attention to them, but as a result he will receive a “dry” translation.

The transfer of stylistic units is one of the most important tasks of translation. He should be given special attention. There are certain stylistic requirements that a translation must meet, that is, normative rules that characterize texts of a similar type in the target language. These requirements include:

Semantic correspondence. Depending on the style and direction of the translation, the translator should always strive to ensure that the translated text reflects the true meaning of the original. Semantic correspondence includes stylistic accuracy, adequacy and completeness.

Literacy. The main requirement is that the text conforms to the general norms of Russian and foreign languages. As a rule, it is assumed that there are no stylistic, grammatical or spelling errors.

Lexical and stylistic correspondence. It is assumed that the correct selection of equivalents of the original terms, the search for analogues of abbreviations and abbreviations, and correct transliteration. The general style of the translated text and the style of the original should not differ in perception. Technical translations are characterized by precision of phrases, absence of emotionally charged words, construction of simple sentences, and impersonality.

In order for the speech to meet the basic stylistic requirements, to be expressive, accurate, stylistically motivated, and for the means used in it to be the most appropriate for expressing the given content and appropriate in the given context, the speaker must master the stylistic resources of the language and know its stylistic norms.

Translation, both oral and written, is a rather complex and multifaceted process. Translation is not simply replacing one language with another. In translation, different cultures, personalities, levels of development, traditions and attitudes collide. The main task of the translator has always been and remains to remember all the difficulties of translation and try to express the author’s thoughts as accurately as possible, while not forgetting to convey the author’s various artistic techniques. As already mentioned, awareness of these difficulties is a step towards success in the professional activity of a translator. A translator's confidence in his abilities should not turn into self-confidence, and his existing knowledge into a frozen dogma that cannot be tested or improved. It is important to remember: translation is, first of all, a difficult, painstaking, responsible work that requires not only versatile knowledge and creative attitude, but also a great desire to convey the author’s idea as clearly as possible. Let us note that such a transfer is virtually impossible to fully implement, and literary translation

will only be an attempt to reproduce by means of another language the entire set of techniques of the original, a kind of variation on the theme of the original.

References:

1. Зубанова И.В. Скоропись в последовательном переводе. Английский язык (с аудио- и видеоприложением). Москва: Р. Валент, 2013.
2. Красовский Д.И., Чужакин А.П. Конференц – перевод (теория и практика). 2-е издание, исправленное и дополненное. Москва: Р. Валент, 2015.
3. Абсаматова Г. Б. LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SIGN LANGUAGE AUTOMATIZATION //МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 3.
4. Abdimital B. THE IMPACT OF CHILDREN’S LITERATURE ON COGNITIVE AND EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT //Конференция: Союз Науки и Образования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 2. – С. 46-50.
5. Abdimital o’g’li A. B. Leksik Birliklarning Lingvomadaniy Xususiyatlari (“Shum Bola” Asarining Tarjimasi Misolida) //Miasto Przyszłości. – 2023. – Т. 34. – С. 236-239.
6. Abdimital o’g’li A. B. FRAZEOLGIK BIRLIKLARNING LINGVOMADANIY XUSUSIYATLARI //IQRO. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 601-603.
7. Bakhodirovna A. G. REQUIREMENTS FOR THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF AN INTERPRETER IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 27. – №. 2. – С. 71-74.
8. Daminov N. K., Nurullayeva S. N. THE FEATURES OF INTERPRETING AND IT’S USE //ВЕСТНИК МАГИСТРАТУРЫ. – 2022. – Т. 5. – С. 155.
9. Daminov N. K. SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION INTERPRETING AS A MODERN TYPE OF TRANSLATION //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 2. – С. 77-81.
10. Daminov N. Using some strategies in simultaneous interpreting process //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 381.
11. Daminov, N. . (2023). VIEWS ABOUT SIGHT TRANSLATION AND SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION. Молодые ученые, 1(21), 34–36.
12. Daminov , N. . (2023). SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING IN THE MODERN CENTURY. Наука и инновация, 1(34), 102–104.
13. Кулдошов У. Конверсивлик ҳодисасининг лингвистик табиати //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 78. – С. 96-101.